

Luminous flux and illumination through general surfaces

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We view general receiver surfaces and extended light sources. First it is assumed that the whole room is a vacuum. We need the more-dimensional integral calculus.

We have a light source with the volume $V(t)$ [$t = \text{time}$] and a receiver with the surface $A(t)$. (see fig.)

We are searching the luminous flux which moves through $A(t)$.

We need the transformation formula of the more-dimensional integral calculus see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §13 theorem 2 p.120:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi: U &\longrightarrow V & y &\in U \\ f: V &\longrightarrow R & x &\in V \\ & & U, V &\subset R^n \end{aligned}$$

$D\varphi =$ Jacobi-matrix of φ

$$\int_U f(\varphi(y)) |\det D\varphi(y)| d^n y = \int_V f(x) d^n x \quad (1)$$

U and V are open sets. φ, φ^{-1} must be continuous differentiable. φ must be bijective.

We use the integral over k -dimensional submanifold, see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §3 p.29 und §14 p.136-138.

Let be $M \subset R^n$ k -dimensional submanifold.

$$f : M \rightarrow R$$

We assume that **one** chart

$$\varphi : T \rightarrow V \subset M \quad (T \subset R^k \text{ open})$$

exists. It is valid $f(M \setminus V) = 0 \quad t \in T \quad x \in V \subset M$

$$\int_M f(x) dS(x) := \int_T f(\varphi(t)) \sqrt{g(t)} d^k t \quad (2)$$

$g(t)$ is the Gram's determinant of φ

$$g(t) = \det G \quad G = (D\varphi)^T \cdot D\varphi$$

$(D\varphi)^T$ is the transpose matrix of $D\varphi$. The matrix G is called metric tensor. In Forster [1] "Analysis" 3 §14 p. 132, 134 are the exact definitions of immersions and charts.

The light source has the volume $V(t)$ and the surface $B(t)$. We introduce one chart $\vec{e}(\vec{y}, t)$ for the surface $B(t)$:

$$B(t) = \vec{e}(\vec{y}, t) \quad \text{with} \quad \vec{y} \in U \subset R^2$$

It shall be: $\vec{b} \in B(t)$.

At the light source the surface radiates. We can imagine the light source as a radiating area. This motivates the surface luminous intensity density $w(\vec{b}, t)$ of the light source.

The relation with the luminous intensity I is:

$$I(t) = \int_{B(t)} w(\vec{b}, t) d\vec{b} \quad \vec{b} \in B(t) \quad (3)$$

unit of $w(\vec{b}, t) = \text{Cd m}^{-2}$

We transform this formula with (2), we obtain:

$$I(t) = \int_U w(\vec{e}(\vec{y}, t), t) \cdot \sqrt{g_e(\vec{y})} d\vec{y} \quad (4)$$

with

$$g_e(\vec{y}) := \det G_e \quad G_e = (D\vec{e})^T \cdot D\vec{e} \quad D\vec{e} := D\vec{e}(\vec{y})$$

Then we have an 2-dimensional integral.

Let be $a \in R^3 \setminus V(t)$ then the illumination $\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t)$ can be written:

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \int_{B(t)} w(\vec{b}, t) \cdot \frac{\vec{a} - \vec{b}}{|\vec{a} - \vec{b}|^3} d\vec{b} \quad (5)$$

The formula is similar to a general formula to the electric field $\vec{E}$. If $\varphi(\vec{b})$ is the surface charge density and ε_0 the electric field constant, the formula is:

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\varepsilon_0} \cdot \int_{B(t)} \varphi(\vec{b}) \cdot \frac{\vec{a} - \vec{b}}{|\vec{a} - \vec{b}|^3} d\vec{b} \quad (6)$$

see Becker [2] chapter 1.3 equation (1.3.11) p.12

The formula (5) is an integral over a surface (2-dimensional submanifold). We can use formula (2) again.

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \int_U w(\vec{e}(\vec{y}, t), t) \cdot \frac{(\vec{a} - \vec{e}(\vec{y}, t))}{|\vec{a} - \vec{e}(\vec{y}, t)|^3} \cdot \sqrt{g_e(\vec{y})} d\vec{y} \quad (7)$$

$$\vec{y} \in U \subset R^2$$

with

$$g_e(\vec{y}) := \det G_e \quad G_e = (D\vec{e})^T \cdot D\vec{e} \\ D\vec{e} := D\vec{e}(\vec{y})$$

A 2-dimensional integral is resulted again. We can possibly do a further transformation with formula (1) to simplify.

special case: the point source with position $\vec{x}$

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \frac{I(t) \cdot (\vec{a} - \vec{x})}{|\vec{a} - \vec{x}|^3} \quad I = \text{light intensity} \quad (8)$$

$$\vec{x} \neq \vec{a}$$

If we view the following figure:

light source

$\vec{n}_B$ = exterior normal unit vector of $B(t)$

Then we see, that $\angle(\vec{n}_B, (\vec{a} - \vec{b})) \leq 90^\circ$ is a necessary condition, that the point $\vec{a}$ is attained.

This condition is not sufficient at light sources, for example, not at the following light source(see figure).

At (5) respectively (7) we need possibly only an integration over a subset of $B(t)$ respectively U .

calculation of $\vec{n}_B(\vec{y})$:

$$\vec{e} : U \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow B(t)$$

$\vec{e}(\vec{y}, t)$ is a parametrization of the surface $B(t)$. $\vec{y} \in U \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ $\vec{y} = (y_1, y_2)$
 exterior normal unit vector:

$$\pm \vec{n}_B(\vec{y}) = \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \vec{e}(\vec{y}, t) \times \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \vec{e}(\vec{y}, t)}{\left| \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \vec{e}(\vec{y}, t) \times \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \vec{e}(\vec{y}, t) \right|} \quad (9)$$

$\frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \vec{c}(\vec{y}, t)$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \vec{c}(\vec{y}, t)$ are tangent vectors at
 $\vec{c}: U \times R \rightarrow B(t)$

see Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §15 theorem 1 p.148.

The restrictive condition can be written, if $\alpha(t) = \angle(\vec{n}_B, \vec{a} - \vec{b})$:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(t) \leq 90^\circ &\quad \Rightarrow \quad \cos \alpha(t) \geq 0 \\ \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\vec{n}_B(\vec{y}) \cdot (\vec{a} - \vec{b})}{|\vec{n}_B(\vec{y})| \cdot |\vec{a} - \vec{b}|} &= \cos \alpha(t) \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

or

$$\vec{n}_B(\vec{y}) \cdot (\vec{a} - \vec{b}) \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

Now we want to calculate the luminous flux through the receiver $A(t)$. The luminous flux is:

$$\Phi(t) = \left| \int_{A(t)} \vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) \cdot \vec{n}_A(\vec{a}) d\vec{a} \right| \quad \vec{a} \in A(t) \quad (12)$$

$\vec{n}_A$ = exterior normal unit vector of $A(t)$

$|\cdot|$ = absolute value

parametrization: $\vec{c}: V \times R \rightarrow A(t) \quad \vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) = A(t)$

$\vec{c}$ is a chart of $A(t)$. $\vec{p} \in V \subset R^2$

transformation with (2):

$$\Phi(t) = \left| \int_V \vec{E}(\vec{c}(\vec{p}, t), t) \cdot \vec{n}_A(\vec{p}) \cdot \sqrt{g_c(\vec{p})} d\vec{p} \right| \quad (13)$$

with

$$g_c(\vec{p}) := \det G_c \quad G_c = (D\vec{c})^T \cdot D\vec{c} \quad D\vec{c} := D\vec{c}(\vec{p})$$

We can possibly do a further transformation with (1) to simplify (13).

If (8) is combined with (12) the result is the luminous flux with a point source.

$\vec{x}$ = position of the point source

$$\Phi(t) = I(t) \cdot \left| \int_{A(t)} \frac{(\vec{a} - \vec{x})}{|\vec{a} - \vec{x}|^3} \cdot \vec{n}_A(\vec{a}) d\vec{a} \right| \quad (14)$$

and for the solid angle Ω von $A(t)$:

$$\Omega = \left| \int_{A(t)} \frac{(\vec{a} - \vec{x})}{|\vec{a} - \vec{x}|^3} \cdot \vec{n}_A(\vec{a}) d\vec{a} \right| \quad \vec{x} \cap A(t) = \emptyset \quad (15)$$

transformation with (2):

$$\vec{c}: V \times R \longrightarrow A(t) \quad \vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) = A(t) \quad \vec{p} \in V \subset R^2$$

$$\Omega = \left| \int_V \frac{(\vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) - \vec{x})}{|\vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) - \vec{x}|^3} \cdot \vec{n}_A(\vec{c}(\vec{p}, t)) \cdot \sqrt{g_c(\vec{p})} d\vec{p} \right| \quad (16)$$

with

$$g_c(\vec{p}) = \det [(D\vec{c}(\vec{p}))^T \cdot D\vec{c}(\vec{p})]$$

Another possibility for Ω can be found in Forster [1] "Analysis 3" §21 problem 21.7 b),c) p.277.

At (12) - (16) we possibly integrate only over a subset of $A(t)$ respectively V see figure.

A necessary but not a sufficient condition, that $\vec{a}$ is attained:

$$\beta(t) = \angle(\vec{E}(\vec{a}), \vec{n}_A(\vec{a})) \geq 90^\circ$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\vec{n}_A(\vec{a}) \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{a})}{|\vec{n}_A(\vec{a})| \cdot |\vec{E}(\vec{a})|} = \cos \beta(t) \leq 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\Rightarrow \vec{n}_A(\vec{a}) \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{a}) \leq 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\vec{c}: V \times R \longrightarrow A(t) \quad \vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) = A(t) \quad \vec{p} = (p_1, p_2) \in V \subset R^2$$

is the parametrization of $A(t)$.

$$\pm \vec{n}_A(\vec{p}) = \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial p_1} \vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) \times \frac{\partial}{\partial p_2} \vec{c}(\vec{p}, t)}{\left| \frac{\partial}{\partial p_1} \vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) \times \frac{\partial}{\partial p_2} \vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) \right|} \quad (19)$$

is the exterior normal unit vector. (19) follows as (9).
with (18) we get:

$$\vec{n}_A(\vec{p}) \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{c}(\vec{p}, t)) \leq 0 \quad (20)$$

We assume a medium with constant density is in the whole room. Then the medium is called homogen. Then in the equations of the illumination the factor e^{-ms} must be added. m is the absorption coefficient, and s is the distance that the light has covered. We view only the visual wavelengths. The gas shall be pure air with about 80% pure nitrogen and about 20% pure oxygen and perhaps (for less than 1%) carbon dioxide.

In this situation the main component of the absorption is the Rayleigh-scattering, the pure absorption is very small. Then it is valid $m \left[\frac{1}{\text{Meter}} \right] \ll 1$. Further information about the Rayleigh scattering coefficient can be found at * at the end of the text.

To that we define:

$$e(\vec{a}, \vec{x}) := e^{-m \cdot |\vec{a} - \vec{x}|} \quad \vec{a}, \vec{x} \in R^3 \quad (21)$$

with m as absorption coefficient.

Then the formulas can be written:

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \int_{B(t)} w(\vec{b}, t) \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{b}) \cdot \frac{\vec{a} - \vec{b}}{|\vec{a} - \vec{b}|^3} d\vec{b} \quad (22)$$

transformation with (2):

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \int_U w(\vec{c}(\vec{y}, t), t) \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{c}(\vec{y}, t)) \cdot \frac{(\vec{a} - \vec{c}(\vec{y}, t))}{|\vec{a} - \vec{c}(\vec{y}, t)|^3} \cdot \sqrt{g_e(\vec{y})} d\vec{y} \quad (23)$$

$$\vec{y} \in U \subset R^2$$

with

$$g_e(\vec{y}) := \det G_e \quad G_e = (D\vec{c})^T \cdot D\vec{c} \quad D\vec{c} := D\vec{c}(\vec{y})$$

Sometimes it is possible to do a further transformation with formula (1) to simplify formula (23).

The same restrictions are valid to the integration sets as in (6) and (7). The

formulas (12) and (13) of luminous flux remain unchanged.
 special case: point source with position $\vec{x}$

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \frac{I(t) \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{x}) \cdot (\vec{a} - \vec{x})}{|\vec{a} - \vec{x}|^3} \quad \vec{x} \neq \vec{a} \quad (24)$$

luminous flux with point source with (12):

$$\Phi(t) = I(t) \cdot \left| \int_{A(t)} \frac{(\vec{a} - \vec{x})}{|\vec{a} - \vec{x}|^3} \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{n}_A(\vec{a}) d\vec{a} \right| \quad (25)$$

$$A(t) \cap \vec{x} = \emptyset$$

transformation with (2):

$$\vec{c}: V \times R \longrightarrow A(t) \quad \vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) = A(t) \quad \vec{p} \in V \subset R^2.$$

$$\Phi(t) = I(t) \cdot \left| \int_V \frac{(\vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) - \vec{x})}{|\vec{c}(\vec{p}, t) - \vec{x}|^3} \cdot e(\vec{c}(\vec{p}, t), \vec{x}) \cdot \vec{n}_A(\vec{c}(\vec{p}, t)) \cdot \sqrt{g_c(\vec{p})} d\vec{p} \right| \quad (26)$$

with

$$g_c(\vec{p}) = \det [(D\vec{c}(\vec{p}))^T \cdot D\vec{c}(\vec{p})]$$

Now we still view shortly line light sources with the parametrization $L(t) = \vec{c}(s, t) \quad s \in U \subset R$
 see fig.

This case can be treated with formula (2) for $n=3$ and $k=1$.
Then it is:

$$G := (D\varphi)^T \cdot D\varphi = (D\vec{e}(s, t))^T \cdot D\vec{e}(s, t)$$

with $\vec{e} = (e_1, e_2, e_3)$

$$= \left(\frac{\partial e_1}{\partial s}, \frac{\partial e_2}{\partial s}, \frac{\partial e_3}{\partial s} \right) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial e_1}{\partial s} \\ \frac{\partial e_2}{\partial s} \\ \frac{\partial e_3}{\partial s} \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{\partial e_i}{\partial s} \right)^2 \quad (27)$$

$$\sqrt{g} = \sqrt{\det G} = \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \begin{pmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ e_3 \end{pmatrix} \right| = \left| \frac{\partial \vec{e}}{\partial s} \right| \quad (28)$$

$|\cdot|$ is the euclidean value of the vector.

We introduce a line luminous intensity density $\bar{w}(\vec{b}, t)$ with the equation:

$$I(t) = \int_{L(t)} \bar{w}(\vec{b}, t) d\vec{b} \quad \vec{b} \in L(t) \subset R^3 \quad (29)$$

(29) can be transformed with (2).

The unit of $\bar{w}(\vec{b}, t)$ is $\frac{\text{Cd}}{\text{m}}$.

With formula (22) we obtain:

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \int_{L(t)} \bar{w}(\vec{b}, t) \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{b}) \cdot \frac{\vec{a} - \vec{b}}{|\vec{a} - \vec{b}|^3} d\vec{b} \quad (30)$$

transformation with (2):

$$\vec{e}: U \times R \longrightarrow L(t) \subset R^3 \quad U \subset R$$

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \int_U \bar{w}(\vec{e}(s, t), t) \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{e}(s, t)) \cdot \frac{(\vec{a} - \vec{e}(s, t))}{|\vec{a} - \vec{e}(s, t)|^3} \cdot \sqrt{g(s)} ds \quad (31)$$

$$s \in U \subset R$$

thus with (28):

$$\vec{E}(\vec{a}, t) = \int_U \bar{w}(\vec{e}(s, t), t) \cdot e(\vec{a}, \vec{e}(s, t)) \cdot \frac{(\vec{a} - \vec{e}(s, t))}{|\vec{a} - \vec{e}(s, t)|^3} \cdot \left| \frac{\partial \vec{e}}{\partial s}(s, t) \right| ds \quad (32)$$

$$s \in U \subset R$$

This is an 1-dimensional integral, that can possibly simplify through a transformation with formula (1). The luminous flux is calculated with (12) respectively (13). Formulas (31) and (32) are like as a line integral in R^3 see Bronstein [4] chapter 3.1.8 p. 318-320. This calculation is suitable for line sources. Here there can be restrictions relative to the integration set.

A remark regarding integrals:

1-dimensional integrals can be treated favourably with the methods of the numerical mathematics. 3-dimensional integrals can be calculated better with the Monte-Carlo-method (a stochastically method). For 2-dimensional integrals the numerical integration and the Monte-Carlo-method can be used. The light sources in this text must not be **Lambert-radiators, neither approximately.**

to *

Calculation of the Rayleigh scattering coefficient h :

In Fabelinskii [3] Chapter IV.14 p.247 table 6

$R_{90} = (1.818 \pm 0.016) \cdot 10^{-8} \text{cm}^{-1}$ is given for pure air to the wavelength $\lambda = 4350 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{m} = 435 \text{nm}$.

It is valid $h = \frac{16}{3}\pi R_{90}$ see [9] Chapter I.1 formula (1.72) p.38.

Because of $R_{90} \sim \frac{1}{\lambda^4}$ see Fabelinskii [3] Chapter I.1 formula (1.69) p.37 and

Chapter IV.14 formula (14.6) p.250 [λ = wavelength] it is possible to convert on other wavelengths.

Then we obtain:

$$h = \frac{16}{3} \pi (1.818 \pm 0.016) \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot \left(\frac{435 \text{nm}}{\lambda[\text{nm}]} \right)^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

thus

$$h[\text{cm}^{-1}] = (30.46 \pm 0.268) \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot \left(\frac{435 \text{nm}}{\lambda[\text{nm}]} \right)^4$$

or

$$h[\text{m}^{-1}] = (30.46 \pm 0.268) \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \left(\frac{435 \text{nm}}{\lambda[\text{nm}]} \right)^4$$

This formula is valid for the visual wavelength area (from 380 nm till 780 nm). Pure air must be present (about 80 % pure nitrogen, about 20 % pure oxygen and perhaps carbon dioxide (for less than 1 %)).

Under these conditions it is valid $h \approx m$, because the pure absorption coefficient is very small.

In dirty air or fog h and m are bigger.

In this text the medium is always pure air then it is:

$$h[\text{m}^{-1}] \approx m[\text{m}^{-1}] \ll 1[\text{m}^{-1}]$$

In labor the attenuation is scarcely perceptible, but at larger distances for example over 1 km this effect cannot be neglected.

References

- [1] Otto Forster "Analysis 3" 2.edition 1983 Vieweg Verlag Brunswick
- [2] Becker/Sauter "Theorie der Elektrizität Band 1" 21.edition 1973 B.G. Teubner Stuttgart
- [3] Immanuel L. Fabelinskii "Molecular Scattering of Light" New York 1968
- [4] I.N. Bronstein, K.A. Semendjajew "Taschenbuch der Mathematik" Teubner Verlagsgesellschaft Leipsic 1985 22.edition
- [5] Harald Schröder "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001